

Formal verification of critical PLC programs and neural network controllers at CERN

Borja Fernández Adiego

*Contains joint work of several members and former members of the **BE-ICS group at CERN***

Roadmap

Context – CERN (European Organization for Nuclear Research)

Context – CERN (European Organization for Nuclear Research)

- CERN has the biggest particle accelerator complex in the world and **many critical and complex industrial installations**

Context – CERN (European Organization for Nuclear Research)

- CERN has the biggest particle accelerator complex in the world and **many critical and complex industrial installations**

LHC
(Large Hadron Collider)

Context – CERN (European Organization for Nuclear Research)

- CERN has the biggest particle accelerator complex in the world and **many critical and complex industrial installations**

LHC
(Large Hadron Collider)

Access and
protection
systems

Context – CERN (European Organization for Nuclear Research)

- CERN has the biggest particle accelerator complex in the world and **many critical and complex industrial installations**

LHC
(Large Hadron Collider)

Access and
protection
systems

Cryogenics plants

Context – CERN (European Organization for Nuclear Research)

- CERN has the biggest particle accelerator complex in the world and **many critical and complex industrial installations**

LHC
(Large Hadron Collider)

Access and
protection
systems

Cryogenics plants

Cooling and ventilation
systems

Context – CERN (European Organization for Nuclear Research)

- CERN has the biggest particle accelerator complex in the world and **many critical and complex industrial installations**

LHC
(Large Hadron Collider)

Access and
protection
systems

Cryogenics plants

Cooling and ventilation
systems

Superconducting magnet test benches

BE-ICS group in a nutshell

BE-ICS group in a nutshell

- “BE-ICS provides the **technology, frameworks, engineering** and CERN-wide **support** for systems and projects in all domains using standard **industrial control** solutions” <https://be-dep-ics.web.cern.ch>

BE-ICS group in a nutshell

- “BE-ICS provides the **technology, frameworks, engineering** and CERN-wide **support** for systems and projects in all domains using standard **industrial control** solutions” <https://be-dep-ics.web.cern.ch>
- BE-ICS is in charge of the design and development of industrial **control** and **safety** systems

CERN control centre

Cooling and ventilation systems

Superconducting magnet test benches

Cryogenics plants

BE-ICS group in a nutshell

- “BE-ICS provides the **technology, frameworks, engineering** and CERN-wide **support** for systems and projects in all domains using standard **industrial control solutions**” <https://be-dep-ics.web.cern.ch>
- BE-ICS is in charge of the design and development of industrial **control** and **safety** systems

WinCCOA

Industrial PCs (FEC)

Programmable Logic Controllers (PLC)

CERN control centre

Cooling and ventilation systems

Superconducting magnet test benches

Cryogenics plants

Context – PLCs at CERN

Context – PLCs at CERN

- At CERN, more than 3000 **PLCs** (Programmable Logic Controllers) are installed to **control** and/or **protect** the installations

Context – PLCs at CERN

- At CERN, more than 3000 **PLCs** (Programmable Logic Controllers) are installed to **control** and/or **protect** the installations

Context – PLCs at CERN

- At CERN, more than 3000 **PLCs** (Programmable Logic Controllers) are installed to **control** and/or **protect** the installations

Example of PLC program

```
(* MODE MANAGER *)
IF NOT (#HLD AND #PHLD) THEN
  (* Forced Mode *)
  IF (#AuMoSt_aux OR #MMoSt_aux OR #SoftLDSt_aux) AND
  #E_MFoMoR AND NOT (#AuIhFoMo) THEN

    #AuMoSt_aux := FALSE;
    #MMoSt_aux := FALSE;
    #FoMoSt_aux := TRUE;
    #SoftLDSt_aux := FALSE;

  (* Software Local Mode *)
  ELSIF (#AuMoSt_aux OR #MMoSt_aux) AND #E_MSoftLDR AND NOT #AuIhFoMo THEN

    #AuMoSt_aux := FALSE;
    #MMoSt_aux := FALSE;
    #FoMoSt_aux := FALSE;
    #SoftLDSt_aux := TRUE;

  (* Manual Mode *)
  ELSIF (#AuMoSt_aux OR #FoMoSt_aux OR #SoftLDSt_aux) AND
  #E_MMMoR AND NOT (#AuIhMMo) THEN

    #AuMoSt_aux := FALSE;
    #MMoSt_aux := TRUE;
    #FoMoSt_aux := FALSE;
    #SoftLDSt_aux := FALSE;

  (* Auto Mode *)
  ELSIF (#MMoSt_aux AND (#E_MAuMoR OR #E_AuAuMoR)) OR
  (#FoMoSt_aux AND #E_MAuMoR) OR
  (#SoftLDSt_aux AND #E_MAuMoR) OR
  (#MMoSt_aux AND #AuIhMMo) OR
  (#FoMoSt_aux AND #AuIhFoMo) OR
  (#SoftLDSt_aux AND #AuIhFoMo) OR
  NOT (#AuMoSt_aux OR #MMoSt_aux OR #FoMoSt_aux OR #SoftLDSt_aux) THEN

    #AuMoSt_aux := TRUE;
```

Context – PLCs at CERN

- At CERN, more than 3000 **PLCs** (Programmable Logic Controllers) are installed to **control** and/or **protect** the installations

Example of specification (ambiguous and incomplete)

Example of PLC program

```

(* MODE MANAGER *)
IF NOT (#HLD AND #PHLD) THEN
  (* Forced Mode *)
  IF (#AuMoSt_aux OR #MMoSt_aux OR #SoftLDSt_aux) AND
  #E_MFoMoR AND NOT (#AuIhFoMo) THEN

    #AuMoSt_aux := FALSE;
    #MMoSt_aux := FALSE;
    #FoMoSt_aux := TRUE;
    #SoftLDSt_aux := FALSE;

  (* Software Local Mode *)
  ELSIF (#AuMoSt_aux OR #MMoSt_aux) AND #E_MSoftLDR AND NOT #AuIhFoMo THEN

    #AuMoSt_aux := FALSE;
    #MMoSt_aux := FALSE;
    #FoMoSt_aux := FALSE;
    #SoftLDSt_aux := TRUE;

  (* Manual Mode *)
  ELSIF (#AuMoSt_aux OR #FoMoSt_aux OR #SoftLDSt_aux) AND
  #E_MMoR AND NOT (#AuIhMMo) THEN

    #AuMoSt_aux := FALSE;
    #MMoSt_aux := TRUE;
    #FoMoSt_aux := FALSE;
    #SoftLDSt_aux := FALSE;

  (* Auto Mode *)
  ELSIF (#MMoSt_aux AND (#E_MAuMoR OR #E_AuAuMoR)) OR
  (#FoMoSt_aux AND #E_MAuMoR) OR
  (#SoftLDSt_aux AND #E_MAuMoR) OR
  (#MMoSt_aux AND #AuIhMMo) OR
  (#FoMoSt_aux AND #AuIhFoMo) OR
  (#SoftLDSt_aux AND #AuIhFoMo) OR
  NOT (#AuMoSt_aux OR #MMoSt_aux OR #FoMoSt_aux OR #SoftLDSt_aux) THEN

    #AuMoSt_aux := TRUE;
  
```

Context – PLCs at CERN

- At CERN, more than 3000 **PLCs** (Programmable Logic Controllers) are installed to **control** and/or **protect** the installations

Example of PLC program

```
(* MODE MANAGER *)
IF NOT (#HLD AND #PHLD) THEN
  (* Forced Mode *)
  IF (#AuMoSt_aux OR #MMoSt_aux OR #SoftLDst_aux) AND
  #E_MFoMoR AND NOT (#AuIhFoMo) THEN

  #AuMoSt_aux := FALSE;
  #MMoSt_aux := FALSE;
  #FoMoSt_aux := TRUE;
  #SoftLDst_aux := FALSE;

  (* Software Local Mode *)
  ELSIF (#AuMoSt_aux OR #MMoSt_aux) AND #E_MSoftLDR AND NOT #AuIhFoMo THEN

  #AuMoSt_aux := FALSE;
  #MMoSt_aux := FALSE;
  #FoMoSt_aux := FALSE;
  #SoftLDst_aux := TRUE;

  (* Manual Mode *)
  ELSIF (#AuMoSt_aux OR #FoMoSt_aux OR #SoftLDst_aux) AND
  #E_MMoR AND NOT (#AuIhMo) THEN

  #AuMoSt_aux := FALSE;
  #MMoSt_aux := TRUE;
  #FoMoSt_aux := FALSE;
  #SoftLDst_aux := FALSE;

  (* Auto Mode *)
  ELSIF (#MMoSt_aux AND (#E_MAuMoR OR #E_AuAuMoR)) OR
  (#FoMoSt_aux AND #E_MAuMoR) OR
  (#SoftLDst_aux AND #E_MAuMoR) OR
  (#MMoSt_aux AND #AuIhMo) OR
  (#FoMoSt_aux AND #AuIhFoMo) OR
  (#SoftLDst_aux AND #AuIhFoMo) OR
  NOT (#AuMoSt_aux OR #MMoSt_aux OR #FoMoSt_aux OR #SoftLDst_aux) THEN
  #AuMoSt_aux := TRUE;

```

Example of specification (ambiguous and incomplete)

Need to guarantee “complex” properties

if **MMoSt** and **AuAuMoR** at any time before the end of the PLC cycle,
then **AuMoSt** should be true at the end of the same PLC cycle

Context – PLCs at CERN

- At CERN, more than 3000 PLCs (Programmable Logic Controllers) are installed to **control** and/or **protect** the installations

Example of PLC program

```
(* MODE MANAGER *)
IF NOT (#HLD AND #PHLD) THEN
  (* Forced Mode *)
  IF (#AuMoSt_aux OR #MMoSt_aux OR #SoftLDSt_aux) AND
  #E_MFoMoR AND NOT (#AuIhFoMo) THEN

    #AuMoSt_aux := FALSE;
    #MMoSt_aux := FALSE;
    #FoMoSt_aux := TRUE;
    #SoftLDSt_aux := FALSE;

  (* Software Local Mode *)
  ELSIF (#AuMoSt_aux OR #MMoSt_aux) AND #E_MSoftLDR AND NOT #AuIhFoMo THEN

    #AuMoSt_aux := FALSE;
    #MMoSt_aux := FALSE;
    #FoMoSt_aux := FALSE;
    #SoftLDSt_aux := TRUE;

  (* Manual Mode *)
  ELSIF (#AuMoSt_aux OR #FoMoSt_aux OR #SoftLDSt_aux) AND
  #E_MMoR AND NOT (#AuIhMo) THEN

    #AuMoSt_aux := FALSE;
    #MMoSt_aux := TRUE;
    #FoMoSt_aux := FALSE;
    #SoftLDSt_aux := FALSE;

  (* Auto Mode *)
  ELSIF (#MMoSt_aux AND (#E_MAuMoR OR #E_AuAuMoR)) OR
  (#FoMoSt_aux AND #E_MAuMoR) OR
  (#SoftLDSt_aux AND #E_MAuMoR) OR
  (#MMoSt_aux AND #AuIhMo) OR
  (#FoMoSt_aux AND #AuIhFoMo) OR
  (#SoftLDSt_aux AND #AuIhFoMo) OR
  NOT (#AuMoSt_aux OR #MMoSt_aux OR #FoMoSt_aux OR #SoftLDSt_aux) THEN
    #AuMoSt_aux := TRUE;
  END IF
END IF
```

Example of specification (ambiguous and incomplete)

Need to guarantee “complex” properties
 if **MMoSt and AuAuMoR** at any time before the end of the PLC cycle,
 then **AuMoSt** should be true at the end of the same PLC cycle

Formal verification
 (e.g. model checking)

Roadmap

Why formal verification?

Pressure Level Temperature

Sensors

Input1
Input2
Input3
Input4

Output1
Output2

Actuators

Why formal verification?

Functionality requirement

If **Input1** is False, then **Output2** is False

Why formal verification?

Functionality requirement

If **Input1** is False, then **Output2** is False

Safety requirement

If **Output1** is False, then **Output2** is True

Why formal verification?

- If "Input1", "Input2", "Input3" and "Input4" are **BOOL**, then we need to check $2^4 = 16$ combinations

Why formal verification?

- If "Input1", "Input2", "Input3" and "Input4" are **BOOL**, then we need to check $2^4 = 16$ combinations
- If they are **INT** (16-bit), then $2^{16*4} \approx 1.8*10^{19}$ combinations

Why formal verification?

- If "Input1", "Input2", "Input3" and "Input4" are **BOOL**, then we need to check $2^4 = 16$ combinations
- If they are **INT** (16-bit), then $2^{16*4} \approx 1.8*10^{19}$ combinations
- for large systems (many variables), such requirements **cannot** (practically) be checked by using testing techniques

Why formal verification?

- If “*Input1*”, “*Input2*”, “*Input3*” and “*Input4*” are **BOOL**, then we need to check $2^4 = 16$ combinations
- If they are **INT** (16-bit), then $2^{16 \cdot 4} \approx 1.8 \cdot 10^{19}$ combinations
- for large systems (many variables), such requirements **cannot** (practically) be checked by using testing techniques
- **Peer reviews** and **testing** can (normally) catch most of the “problems” (e.g. code bugs), but not the **corner cases**

Why formal verification?

- If “*Input1*”, “*Input2*”, “*Input3*” and “*Input4*” are **BOOL**, then we need to check $2^4 = 16$ combinations
- If they are **INT** (16-bit), then $2^{16*4} \approx 1.8*10^{19}$ combinations
- for large systems (many variables), such requirements **cannot** (practically) be checked by using testing techniques
- **Peer reviews** and **testing** can (normally) catch most of the “problems” (e.g. code bugs), but not the **corner cases**
 - **E.g. Ariane 5 rocket explosion** (more than 500 millions US\$ cost due to a software flaw in control software)

Why formal verification?

- If “*Input1*”, “*Input2*”, “*Input3*” and “*Input4*” are **BOOL**, then we need to check $2^4 = 16$ combinations
- If they are **INT** (16-bit), then $2^{16 \cdot 4} \approx 1.8 \cdot 10^{19}$ combinations
- for large systems (many variables), such requirements **cannot** (practically) be checked by using testing techniques
- **Peer reviews** and **testing** can (normally) catch most of the “problems” (e.g. code bugs), but not the **corner cases**
 - **E.g. Ariane 5 rocket explosion** (more than 500 millions US\$ cost due to a software flaw in control software)

Solution: **Model checking**

What are Formal Methods?

What are Formal Methods?

Techniques based on **mathematics** and **formal logic (precise semantics)**

What are Formal Methods?

Techniques based on **mathematics** and **formal logic (precise semantics)**

Graphical languages

Petri nets, automata, ...

What are Formal Methods?

Techniques based on **mathematics** and **formal logic** (precise semantics)

Graphical languages

Petri nets, automata, ...

Automata

Textual languages

B-method, VDM, TLA+,...

B-method

```
MACHINE
  Switch
SETS
  STATE = {closed, open}
VARIABLES
  state
INVARIANT
  state : STATE
INITIALISATION
  state := open
OPERATIONS
  toggle =
    IF state = open
    THEN
      state := closed
    ELSE
      state := open
    END ;
END
```

What are Formal Methods?

Techniques based on **mathematics** and **formal logic** (precise semantics)

Graphical languages

Petri nets, automata, ...

Automata

Textual languages

B-method, VDM, TLA+, ...

B-method

```

MACHINE
  Switch
SETS
  STATE = {closed, open}
VARIABLES
  state
INVARIANT
  state : STATE
INITIALISATION
  state := open
OPERATIONS
  toggle =
    IF state = open
    THEN
      state := closed
    ELSE
      state := open
    END ;
END
  
```

Mathematical languages

Temporal logic,
propositional logic, Z
notation, ...

Temporal logic

$AG((a \wedge b) \rightarrow c)$

Propositional logic

$(A \rightarrow B) \vdash (\neg B \rightarrow \neg A)$

What are Formal Methods?

Techniques based on **mathematics** and **formal logic** (precise semantics)

Graphical languages

Petri nets, automata, ...

e.g. **system model**
(model checking)

Textual languages

B-method, VDM, TLA+,...

B-method

```
MACHINE
  Switch
SETS
  STATE = {closed, open}
VARIABLES
  state
INVARIANT
  state : STATE
INITIALISATION
  state := open
OPERATIONS
  toggle =
    IF state = open
    THEN
      state := closed
    ELSE
      state := open
    END ;
END
```

Mathematical languages

Temporal logic,
propositional logic, Z
notation,...

e.g. **properties**
(model checking)

Temporal logic

$AG((a \wedge b) \rightarrow c)$

Propositional logic

$(A \rightarrow B) \vdash (\neg B \rightarrow \neg A)$

What are Formal Methods?

Techniques based on **mathematics and formal logic (precise semantics)**

Graphical languages

Petri nets, automata, ...

e.g. **system model**
(model checking)

Textual languages

B-method, VDM, TLA+,...

B-method

```
MACHINE
  Switch
SETS
  STATE = {closed, open}
VARIABLES
  state
INVARIANT
  state : STATE
INITIALISATION
  state := open
OPERATIONS
  toggle =
    IF state = open
    THEN
      state := closed
    ELSE
      state := open
    END ;
END
```

Mathematical languages

Temporal logic,
propositional logic, Z
notation,...

e.g. **properties**
(model checking)

Temporal logic

$AG((a \wedge b) \rightarrow c)$

Propositional logic

$(A \rightarrow B) \vdash (\neg B \rightarrow \neg A)$

They can be used for **specification, verification, simulation, test case generation**, etc.

Where are Formal Methods being used?

Formal specification

Formal verification

Where are Formal Methods being used?

Formal specification

COMPASS

Correctness, Modelling and Performance of Aerospace Systems

<http://www.compass-toolset.org>

Using **TLA+** to create a clear and concise specification, leading to a subsequent code reduction <https://cacm.acm.org/magazines/2015/4/184701-how-amazon-web-services-uses-formal-methods/fulltext>

Use of the formal specification language **VDM** to specify industrial applications

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/2879682_The_IFAD_VDM-SL_toolbox

Formal Verification of Critical Aerospace Software <https://hal.archives-ouvertes.fr/hal-01184099/document>

Formal verification

Integration of their **static analyser** INFER into their **software development** process <https://www.inf.ed.ac.uk/teaching/courses/sp/2019/lecs/distefano-scaling-2019.pdf>

NASA AMES Robust Software Engineering group

<https://www.nasa.gov/isd-robust-software-engineering>

Use of the model checker SPIN to verify the model of a software

<http://spinroot.com/gerard/pdf/spin04.pdf>

Verification of **neural-network-based control** systems in non-towered airports to avoid collisions at landing

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/356096882_Formal_Analysis_of_Neural_Network-Based_Systems_in_the_Aircraft_Domain

And many more ...

Why aren't Formal Methods widely used?

Pros	Cons
<i>Unambiguity</i> (well-defined semantics)	<i>High cost</i> (time)
<i>Precision</i> (e.g. software verification)	<i>Limitation of computational models</i> (state space explosion in model checking)
...	<i>Usability</i>

Why aren't Formal Methods widely used?

Pros	Cons
<i>Unambiguity</i> (well-defined semantics)	<i>High cost</i> (time)
<i>Precision</i> (e.g. software verification)	<i>Limitation of computational models</i> (state space explosion in model checking)
...	<i>Usability</i>

- Using formal methods is **more “expensive”** than traditional alternatives in engineering
- Real-life system models may be too large **to be handled by simulators or model checkers**
- We should **apply them when the cost of a failure is higher than the cost of using them** (tool support)

Formal methods and the standards (e.g. functional safety)

Formal methods and the standards (e.g. functional safety)

IEC 61508: Functional safety of electrical/electronic/programmable electronic safety-related systems

Formal methods and the standards (e.g. functional safety)

IEC 61508: Functional safety of electrical/electronic/programmable electronic safety-related systems

Table A.1 – Software safety requirements specification

(See 7.2)

Technique/Measure *		Ref.	SIL 1	SIL 2	SIL 3	SIL 4
1a	Semi-formal methods	Table B.7	R	R	HR	HR
1b	Formal methods	B.2.2, C.2.4	---	R	R	HR
2	Forward traceability between the system safety requirements and the software safety requirements	C.2.11	R	R	HR	HR
3	Backward traceability between the safety requirements and the perceived safety needs	C.2.11	R	R	HR	HR
4	Computer-aided specification tools to support appropriate techniques/measures above	B.2.4	R	R	HR	HR

Formal methods and the standards (e.g. functional safety)

IEC 61508: Functional safety of electrical/electronic/programmable electronic safety-related systems

Table A.1 – Software safety requirements specification

(See 7.2)

Technique/Measure *		Ref.	SIL 1	SIL 2	SIL 3	SIL 4
1a	Semi-formal methods	Table B.7	R	R	HR	HR
1b	Formal methods	B.2.2, C.2.4	---	R	R	HR
2	Forward traceability between the system safety requirements and the software safety requirements	C.2.11	R	R	HR	HR
3	Backward traceability between the safety requirements and the perceived safety needs	C.2.11	R	R	HR	HR
4	Computer-aided specification tools to support appropriate techniques/measures above	B.2.4	R	R	HR	HR

Formal methods and the standards (e.g. functional safety)

IEC 61508: Functional safety of electrical/electronic/programmable electronic safety-related systems

Table A.1 – Software safety requirements specification

(See 7.2)

Technique/Measure *		Ref.	SIL 1	SIL 2	SIL 3	SIL 4
1a	Semi-formal methods	Table B.7	R	R	HR	HR
1b	Formal methods	B.2.2, C.2.4	---	R	R	HR
2	Forward traceability between the system safety requirements and the software safety requirements	C.2.11	R	R	HR	HR
3	Backward traceability between the safety requirements and the perceived safety needs	C.2.11	R	R	HR	HR
4	Computer-aided specification tools to support appropriate techniques/measures above	B.2.4	R	R	HR	HR

Table A.5 – Software design and development – software module testing and integration

(See 7.4.7 and 7.4.8)

Technique/Measure *		Ref.	SIL 1	SIL 2	SIL 3	SIL 4
1	Probabilistic testing	C.5.1	---	R	R	R
2	Dynamic analysis and testing	B.6.5 Table B.2	R	HR	HR	HR
3	Data recording and analysis	C.5.2	HR	HR	HR	HR
4	Functional and black box testing	B.5.1 B.5.2 Table B.3	HR	HR	HR	HR
5	Performance testing	Table B.6	R	R	HR	HR
6	Model based testing	C.5.27	R	R	HR	HR
7	Interface testing	C.5.3	R	R	HR	HR
8	Test management and automation tools	C.4.7	R	HR	HR	HR
9	Forward traceability between the software design specification and the module and integration test specifications	C.2.11	R	R	HR	HR
10	Formal verification	C.5.12	---	---	R	R

Formal methods and the standards (e.g. functional safety)

IEC 61508: Functional safety of electrical/electronic/programmable electronic safety-related systems

Table A.1 – Software safety requirements specification

(See 7.2)

Technique/Measure *		Ref.	SIL 1	SIL 2	SIL 3	SIL 4
1a	Semi-formal methods	Table B.7	R	R	HR	HR
1b	Formal methods	B.2.2, C.2.4	---	R	R	HR
2	Forward traceability between the system safety requirements and the software safety requirements	C.2.11	R	R	HR	HR
3	Backward traceability between the safety requirements and the perceived safety needs	C.2.11	R	R	HR	HR
4	Computer-aided specification tools to support appropriate techniques/measures above	B.2.4	R	R	HR	HR

Table A.5 – Software design and development – software module testing and integration

(See 7.4.7 and 7.4.8)

Technique/Measure *		Ref.	SIL 1	SIL 2	SIL 3	SIL 4
1	Probabilistic testing	C.5.1	---	R	R	R
2	Dynamic analysis and testing	B.6.5 Table B.2	R	HR	HR	HR
3	Data recording and analysis	C.5.2	HR	HR	HR	HR
4	Functional and black box testing	B.5.1 B.5.2 Table B.3	HR	HR	HR	HR
5	Performance testing	Table B.6	R	R	HR	HR
6	Model based testing	C.5.27	R	R	HR	HR
7	Interface testing	C.5.3	R	R	HR	HR
8	Test management and automation tools	C.4.7	R	HR	HR	HR
9	Forward traceability between the software design specification and the module and integration test specifications	C.2.11	R	R	HR	HR
10	Formal verification	C.5.12	---	---	R	R

Formal methods and the standards (e.g. functional safety)

IEC 61508: Functional safety of electrical/electronic/programmable electronic safety-related systems

Table A.1 – Software safety requirements specification

(See 7.2)

Technique/Measure *		Ref.	SIL 1	SIL 2	SIL 3	SIL 4
1a	Semi-formal methods	Table B.7	R	R	HR	HR
1b	Formal methods	B.2.2, C.2.4	---	R	R	HR
2	Forward traceability between the system safety requirements and the software safety requirements	C.2.11	R	R	HR	HR
3	Backward traceability between the safety requirements and the perceived safety needs	C.2.11	R	R	HR	HR
4	Computer-aided specification tools to support appropriate techniques/measures above	B.2.4	R	R	HR	HR

Table A.5 – Software design and development – software module testing and integration

(See 7.4.7 and 7.4.8)

Technique/Measure *		Ref.	SIL 1	SIL 2	SIL 3	SIL 4
1	Probabilistic testing	C.5.1	---	R	R	R
2	Dynamic analysis and testing	B.6.5 Table B.2	R	HR	HR	HR
3	Data recording and analysis	C.5.2	HR	HR	HR	HR
4	Functional and black box testing	B.5.1 B.5.2 Table B.3	HR	HR	HR	HR
5	Performance testing	Table B.6	R	R	HR	HR
6	Model based testing	C.5.27	R	R	HR	HR
7	Interface testing	C.5.3	R	R	HR	HR
8	Test management and automation tools	C.4.7	R	HR	HR	HR
9	Forward traceability between the software design specification and the module and integration test specifications	C.2.11	R	R	HR	HR
10	Formal verification	C.5.12	---	---	R	R

IEC 61511: Functional safety – Safety instrumented systems for the process industry sector

Formal methods and the standards (e.g. functional safety)

IEC 61508: Functional safety of electrical/electronic/programmable electronic safety-related systems

Table A.1 – Software safety requirements specification

(See 7.2)

	Technique/Measure *	Ref.	SIL 1	SIL 2	SIL 3	SIL 4
1a	Semi-formal methods	Table B.7	R	R	HR	HR
1b	Formal methods	B.2.2, C.2.4	---	R	R	HR
2	Forward traceability between the system safety requirements and the software safety requirements	C.2.11	R	R	HR	HR
3	Backward traceability between the safety requirements and the perceived safety needs	C.2.11	R	R	HR	HR
4	Computer-aided specification tools to support appropriate techniques/measures above	B.2.4	R	R	HR	HR

Table A.5 – Software design and development – software module testing and integration

(See 7.4.7 and 7.4.8)

	Technique/Measure *	Ref.	SIL 1	SIL 2	SIL 3	SIL 4
1	Probabilistic testing	C.5.1	---	R	R	R
2	Dynamic analysis and testing	B.6.5 Table B.2	R	HR	HR	HR
3	Data recording and analysis	C.5.2	HR	HR	HR	HR
4	Functional and black box testing	B.5.1 B.5.2 Table B.3	HR	HR	HR	HR
5	Performance testing	Table B.6	R	R	HR	HR
6	Model based testing	C.5.27	R	R	HR	HR
7	Interface testing	C.5.3	R	R	HR	HR
8	Test management and automation tools	C.4.7	R	HR	HR	HR
9	Forward traceability between the software design specification and the module and integration test specifications	C.2.11	R	R	HR	HR
10	Formal verification	C.5.12	---	---	R	R

IEC 61511: Functional safety – Safety instrumented systems for the process industry sector

- several references to model checking. For example from IEC 61511-2:2016 Annex B:

*“... specification should be implemented in the graphical language of the **model checking** workbench environment...”*

Formal methods and the standards (e.g. functional safety)

IEC 61508: Functional safety of electrical/electronic/programmable electronic safety-related systems

Table A.1 – Software safety requirements specification

(See 7.2)

	Technique/Measure *	Ref.	SIL 1	SIL 2	SIL 3	SIL 4
1a	Semi-formal methods	Table B.7	R	R	HR	HR
1b	Formal methods	B.2.2, C.2.4	---	R	R	HR
2	Forward traceability between the system safety requirements and the software safety requirements	C.2.11	R	R	HR	HR
3	Backward traceability between the safety requirements and the perceived safety needs	C.2.11	R	R	HR	HR
4	Computer-aided specification tools to support appropriate techniques/measures above	B.2.4	R	R	HR	HR

Table A.5 – Software design and development – software module testing and integration

(See 7.4.7 and 7.4.8)

	Technique/Measure *	Ref.	SIL 1	SIL 2	SIL 3	SIL 4
1	Probabilistic testing	C.5.1	---	R	R	R
2	Dynamic analysis and testing	B.6.5 Table B.2	R	HR	HR	HR
3	Data recording and analysis	C.5.2	HR	HR	HR	HR
4	Functional and black box testing	B.5.1 B.5.2 Table B.3	HR	HR	HR	HR
5	Performance testing	Table B.6	R	R	HR	HR
6	Model based testing	C.5.27	R	R	HR	HR
7	Interface testing	C.5.3	R	R	HR	HR
8	Test management and automation tools	C.4.7	R	HR	HR	HR
9	Forward traceability between the software design specification and the module and integration test specifications	C.2.11	R	R	HR	HR
10	Formal verification	C.5.12	---	---	R	R

IEC 61511: Functional safety – Safety instrumented systems for the process industry sector

- several references to model checking. For example from IEC 61511-2:2016 Annex B:

“... specification should be implemented in the graphical language of the **model checking** workbench environment...”

Introduction to model checking (for PLC programs)

Introduction to model checking (for PLC programs)

Given a **global model** of the system and a **formal property**, the **model checking algorithm checks exhaustively** that the model meets the property

Clarke and Emerson (1982) and Queille and Sifakis (1982)

Introduction to model checking (for PLC programs)

Given a **global model** of the system and a **formal property**, the **model checking algorithm checks exhaustively** that the model meets the property

Clarke and Emerson (1982) and Queille and Sifakis (1982)

Specifications

Introduction to model checking (for PLC programs)

Given a **global model** of the system and a **formal property**, the **model checking algorithm checks exhaustively** that the model meets the property

Clarke and Emerson (1982) and Queille and Sifakis (1982)

**Formal
model**

Specifications

**Formal
requirement**

Introduction to model checking (for PLC programs)

Given a **global model** of the system and a **formal property**, the **model checking algorithm checks exhaustively** that the model meets the property

Clarke and Emerson (1982) and Queille and Sifakis (1982)

Introduction to model checking (for PLC programs)

Given a **global model** of the system and a **formal property**, the **model checking algorithm checks exhaustively** that the model meets the property

Clarke and Emerson (1982) and Queille and Sifakis (1982)

Introduction to model checking (for PLC programs)

Given a **global model** of the system and a **formal property**, the **model checking algorithm checks exhaustively** that the model meets the property

Clarke and Emerson (1982) and Queille and Sifakis (1982)

Model Checking lectures
(Aachen university)

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Y5Hg4MvUXc4&list=PLwabKnOFhE38C0o6z_bhIF_uOUIbIDTjh

Was born for **hardware design**,
today it is used extensively for
software verification as well

Introduction to model checking (for PLC programs)

Given a **global model** of the system and a **formal property**, the **model checking algorithm checks exhaustively** that the model meets the property

Clarke and Emerson (1982) and Queille and Sifakis (1982)

Model Checking lectures
(Aachen university)

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Y5Hg4MvUXc4&list=PLwabKnOFhE38C0o6z_bhIF_uOUIbIDTjh

Property failed
Trace leading to the violation

Property OK

Was born for **hardware design**,
today it is used extensively for
software verification as well

Introduction to model checking (for PLC programs)

Given a **global model** of the system and a **formal property**, the **model checking algorithm checks exhaustively** that the model meets the property

Clarke and Emerson (1982) and Queille and Sifakis (1982)

Model Checking lectures
(Aachen university)

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Y5Hg4MvUXc4&list=PLwabKnOFhE38C0o6z_bhIF_uOUIbIDTjh

Property failed
Trace leading to the violation

Property OK

Was born for **hardware design**,
today it is used extensively for
software verification as well

Introduction to model checking (for PLC programs)

Given a **global model** of the system and a **formal property**, the **model checking algorithm checks exhaustively** that the model meets the property

Clarke and Emerson (1982) and Queille and Sifakis (1982)

Model Checking lectures
(Aachen university)

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Y5Hg4MvUXc4&list=PLwabKnOFhE38C0o6z_bhIF_uOUIbIDTjh

Property failed
Trace leading to the violation

Property OK

Was born for **hardware design**,
today it is used extensively for
software verification as well

Introduction to model checking (for PLC programs)

Given a **global model** of the system and a **formal property**, the model checking algorithm **checks exhaustively** that the model meets the property

Clarke and Emerson (1982) and Queille and Sifakis (1982)

Model Checking lectures
(Aachen university)

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Y5Hg4MvUXc4&list=PLwabKnOFhE38C0o6z_bhIF_uOUIbIDTjh

Property failed
Trace leading to the violation

Property OK

Was born for **hardware design**, today it is used extensively for **software verification** as well

PLCverif (for users)

PLCverif (for users)

The screenshot displays the PLCverif software interface. The title bar shows 'Pv PLCverif'. The menu bar includes 'File', 'Preferences', and 'Help'. The toolbar contains various icons for file operations and editing. The Project Explorer on the left shows a project structure with folders like 'output' and 'src-gen', and files like 'Demo.scl', 'verifCase1.vc3', 'verifCase2.vc3', and 'verifCase3.vc3'. The main editor window shows the content of 'Demo.scl'.

```
// FUNCTION declaration
FUNCTION FC1 : VOID
  VAR_INPUT
    in1 : BOOL;
    in2 : BOOL;
    in3 : BOOL;
    in4 : BOOL;
  END_VAR
  VAR_OUTPUT
    out1 : BOOL;
    out2 : BOOL;
  END_VAR
BEGIN
  // logic for out1
  IF in1 OR NOT in2 THEN
    out1 := NOT in3 OR in4;
  ELSE
    out1 := FALSE;
  END_IF;

  // logic for out2
  out2 := (in1 OR NOT in2) AND (NOT in3 OR in4);
END_FUNCTION
```

PLCverif (for users)

PLCverif (for users)

PLCverif (for users)

PLCverif (for users)

The screenshot shows the PLCverif application interface. On the left is the Project Explorer showing a tree view of projects and files. The main window displays a verification report for 'verifCase2.vc3'. The report title is 'PLCverif — Verification report'. It includes a table with the following details:

ID:	verifCase2
Name:	
Description:	
Source file(s):	<ul style="list-style-type: none">C:\dev\PLCverif\workspace\1_PBCS_Workshop_DemoSCL\Demo.sclC:\dev\PLCverif\workspace\builtin_Siemens S7-300\builtin.scl
Requirement:	If not FC1.out1 is true at the end of the PLC cycle, then FC1.out2 should always be true at the end of the same cycle.
Result:	Violated
Verification backend:	NusmvBackend (nuxmv-Classic-dynamic-df)
Total run time:	449 ms
Backend run time:	346 ms

Below the report is a 'Counterexample' table:

	Variable	End of Cycle 1
INPUT BOOL	FC1.in1	true
INPUT BOOL	FC1.in2	false
INPUT BOOL	FC1.in3	true
INPUT BOOL	FC1.in4	false
OUTPUT BOOL	FC1.out1	false
OUTPUT BOOL	FC1.out2	false

At the bottom left of the interface, it says 'An outline is not available.'

PLCverif (for users)

The screenshot displays the PLCverif IDE interface. On the left, the Project Explorer shows a tree view of the project structure, including folders like 'output', 'src-gen', and '1_PBCS_Workshop_DemoSCL'. The main window shows a verification report for 'verifCase2.vc3'. The report title is 'PLCverif — Verification report'. It includes a header with the generation date and version, and a table of verification details. The 'Result' field is highlighted in red, indicating a violation. Below the report, a 'Counterexample' table provides the state of variables at the end of cycle 1.

Generated on 2021-12-06 11:50:27 | PLCverif v3.0 | (C) CERN BE-ICS-AP | [Show/hide expert details](#)

ID:	verifCase2
Name:	
Description:	
Source file(s):	<ul style="list-style-type: none">C:\dev\PLCverif\workspace\1_PBCS_Workshop_DemoSCL\Demo.sclC:\dev\PLCverif\workspace\builtin_Siemens_S7-300\builtin.scl
Requirement:	If not FC1.out1 is true at the end of the PLC cycle, then FC1.out2 should always be true at the end of the same cycle.
Result:	Violated
Verification backend:	NusmvBackend (nuxmv-Classic-dynamic-df)
Total run time:	449 ms
Backend run time:	346 ms

Counterexample

	Variable	End of Cycle 1
INPUT BOOL	FC1.in1	true
INPUT BOOL	FC1.in2	false
INPUT BOOL	FC1.in3	true
INPUT BOOL	FC1.in4	false
OUTPUT BOOL	FC1.out1	false
OUTPUT BOOL	FC1.out2	false

PLCverif references: <https://gitlab.com/plcverif-oss> and www.cern.ch/plcverif

The **complexity** of using formal methods **is hidden** by the PLCverif

Some references

Some references

Real case studies

B. Fernández et al. **“Applying model checking to industrial-sized PLC programs”**. In *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics*
<https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/7295624>

B. Fernandez et al. **“Applying model checking to critical PLC applications : An ITER case study”** in Proc. of the 17th ICALEPCS
<https://cds.cern.ch/record/2305319/files/thpha161.pdf>

B. Fernandez et al. **“Applying model checking to highly-configurable safety critical software: The SPS-PPS PLC program”** in Proc. of the 18th ICALEPCS
<https://cds.cern.ch/record/2809709/files/document.pdf>

B. Fernandez et al. **“Cause-and-Effect Matrix specifications for safety critical systems at CERN”** in Proc. of the 17th ICALEPCS
<https://accelconf.web.cern.ch/icalepcs2019/papers/mopha041.pdf>

Some references

Real case studies

 B. Fernández et al. “Applying model checking to industrial-sized PLC programs”. In *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics* <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/7295624>

 B. Fernandez et al. “Applying model checking to critical PLC applications : An ITER case study” in *Proc. of the 17th ICALEPCS* <https://cds.cern.ch/record/2305319/files/thpha161.pdf>

 B. Fernandez et al. “Applying model checking to highly-configurable safety critical software: The SPS-PPS PLC program” in *Proc. of the 18th ICALEPCS* <https://cds.cern.ch/record/2809709/files/document.pdf>

 B. Fernandez et al. “Cause-and-Effect Matrix specifications for safety critical systems at CERN” in *Proc. of the 17th ICALEPCS* <https://accelconf.web.cern.ch/icalepcs2019/papers/mopha041.pdf>

Research activities

 Ignacio D. Lopez-Miguel et al. “Simplification of numeric variables for PLC model checking”. In *Proc. of the MEMOCODE '21* <https://dl.acm.org/doi/abs/10.1145/3487212.3487334>

 Milán Mondok. “Evaluating compositional verification options for PLCverif”. In *CERN internal note* https://cds.cern.ch/record/2780057/files/compositional_verification.pdf

 B. Fernández et al. “Modelling and formal verification of timing aspects in large PLC programs”. In *Proc. of IFAC World Congress'14* <http://cds.cern.ch/record/1956687/files/CERN-ACC-2014-0226.pdf>

 D. Darvas et al. “A formal specification method for PLC-based applications” in *Proc. of the 15th ICALEPCS* <https://accelconf.web.cern.ch/ICALEPCS2015/papers/wepqf091.pdf>

 Zsófia Ádám et al. “From Natural Language Requirements to the Verification of Programmable Logic Controllers: Integrating FRET into PLCverif”. In *NASA Formal Methods Symposium* https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-031-33170-1_21

 Mihály Dobos-Kovács. “Counterexample analysis of formal verification methods”. In *CERN internal note* https://cds.cern.ch/record/2779411/files/MihalyDobosKovacs_report.pdf

Roadmap

First steps

Context – CERN (European Organization for Nuclear Research)

- Many applications of machine learning at CERN

Context – CERN (European Organization for Nuclear Research)

- Many applications of machine learning at CERN

Robotics

Context – CERN (European Organization for Nuclear Research)

- Many applications of machine learning at CERN

Robotics

Data analysis of the physics experiments

Context – CERN (European Organization for Nuclear Research)

- Many applications of machine learning at CERN

Robotics

Data analysis of the physics experiments

Particle accelerators Operation and beam optimization

Context – CERN (European Organization for Nuclear Research)

- Many applications of machine learning at CERN

Robotics

Data analysis of the physics experiments

Particle accelerators Operation and beam optimization

Industrial controls

Context – Neural-network-based controllers

Context – Neural-network-based controllers

Why NN-based controllers?

Context – Neural-network-based controllers

Why NN-based controllers?

Tasks hard to specify

- Autonomous driving

Several rule exceptions

[2] Pisarov, Jelena & Mester, Gyula. (2020). The Future of Autonomous Vehicles. FME Transactions. 49. 29-35. 10.5937/fme2101029P.

Context – Neural-network-based controllers

Why NN-based controllers?

Tasks hard to specify

- Autonomous driving

Computationally fast

- Matrix multiplication

Several rule exceptions

[2] Pisarov, Jelena & Mester, Gyula. (2020). The Future of Autonomous Vehicles. FME Transactions. 49. 29-35. 10.5937/fme2101029P.

Context – Neural-network-based controllers

Why NN-based controllers?

Tasks hard to specify

- Autonomous driving

Several rule exceptions

Computationally fast

- Matrix multiplication

Versatile

- Non-linearities
- No need to linearize

Context – Neural-network-based controllers

Why NN-based controllers?

Tasks hard to specify

- Autonomous driving

[2]

Several rule exceptions

Computationally fast

- Matrix multiplication

Versatile

- Non-linearities
- No need to linearize

Only data needed

- No physical modelling required
- Collect data

Context – Neural-network-based controllers

Why NN-based controllers?

Tasks hard to specify

- Autonomous driving

[2]

Several rule exceptions

Computationally fast

- Matrix multiplication

Versatile

- Non-linearities
- No need to linearize

Only data needed

- No physical modelling required
- Collect data

[2] Pisarov, Jelena & Mester, Gyula. (2020). The Future of Autonomous Vehicles. FME Transactions. 49. 29-35. 10.5937/fme2101029P.

Context – Neural-network-based controllers

Why NN-based controllers?

Tasks hard to specify

- Autonomous driving

[2]

Several rule exceptions

Computationally fast

- Matrix multiplication

Versatile

- Non-linearities
- No need to linearize

Only data needed

- No physical modelling required
- Collect data

But a failure in the controller can be fatal

[2] Pisarov, Jelena & Mester, Gyula. (2020). The Future of Autonomous Vehicles. FME Transactions. 49. 29-35. 10.5937/fme2101029P.

Context – Verification of neural-network-based controllers

Why verification of NNs?

Context – Verification of neural-network-based controllers

Why verification of NNs?

- **Guaranteeing properties**

Context – Verification of neural-network-based controllers

Why verification of NNs?

- **Guaranteeing properties**

Robustness

Dangerous curve to the right

+ noise

Children crossing

Context – Verification of neural-network-based controllers

Why verification of NNs?

- **Guaranteeing properties**

Robustness

Dangerous curve to the right

+ noise

Children crossing

Monotonicity

Context – Verification of neural-network-based controllers

Why verification of NNs?

- **Guaranteeing properties**

Robustness

Dangerous curve to the right

+ noise

Children crossing

Monotonicity

Reachability

Context – Verification of neural-network-based controllers

Why verification of NNs?

- **Guaranteeing properties**

Robustness

Dangerous curve to the right

+ noise

Children crossing

Monotonicity

Safety

Reachability

Context – Verification of neural-network-based controllers

Why verification of NNs?

- **Guaranteeing properties**

Robustness

Dangerous curve to the right

+ noise

Children crossing

Monotonicity

Safety

Reachability

Stability

Context – Verification of neural-network-based controllers

Why verification of NNs?

- **Guaranteeing properties**

- **Explainability**

Robustness

Dangerous curve to the right

+ noise

Children crossing

Monotonicity

Safety

Reachability

Stability

- **Is it possible** that a given situation ever occurs?
- **Is there a combination** of inputs that leads to a given output?

Case study – LHC cooling towers controller

Case study – LHC cooling towers controller

- Induced draft cooling towers (IDCTs)
- **Provide cold water** for different LHC subsystems (e.g. cryogenics, chillers, air handling units, etc.)

Case study – LHC cooling towers controller

- Induced draft cooling towers (IDCTs)
- **Provide cold water** for different LHC subsystems (e.g. cryogenics, chillers, air handling units, etc.)
- **Control actions:**
 - **Mode selection:**
 1. Ventilation
 2. Showering
 3. Bypass
 - **Fan speed**

Case study – LHC cooling towers controller

- Induced draft cooling towers (IDCTs)
- **Provide cold water** for different LHC subsystems (e.g. cryogenics, chillers, air handling units, etc.)
- **Control actions:**
 - **Mode selection:**
 1. Ventilation
 2. Showering
 3. Bypass
 - **Fan speed**
- **Control objective:**
 - Keep **outlet water temperature within strict limits**
 - Utilize **minimum amount of energy**

Case study – LHC cooling towers controller

- Induced draft cooling towers (IDCTs)
- **Provide cold water** for different LHC subsystems (e.g. cryogenics, chillers, air handling units, etc.)
- **Control actions:**
 - **Mode selection:**
 1. Ventilation
 2. Showering
 3. Bypass
 - **Fan speed**
- **Control objective:**
 - Keep **outlet water temperature within strict limits**
 - Utilize **minimum amount of energy**

Case study – LHC cooling towers controller

- Induced draft cooling towers (IDCTs)
- **Provide cold water** for different LHC subsystems (e.g. cryogenics, chillers, air handling units, etc.)
- **Control actions:**
 - **Mode selection:**
 1. Ventilation
 2. Showering
 3. Bypass
 - **Fan speed**
- **Control objective:**
 - Keep **outlet water temperature within strict limits**
 - Utilize **minimum amount of energy**

Case study – NN description

Case study – NN description

Initial non-conventional NN architecture

Case study – NN description

Initial non-conventional NN architecture

Hidden layers

- Feedforward NN with **ReLU** and **SoftMax** activation functions
- Developed and trained with **Python Keras**
- Automatically translated to S7-1200 Siemens PLC Structured Control Language (**SCL**)

Case study

Case study

Properties to be verified

Case study

Properties to be verified

Operational modes reachability

Do these inputs exist?

Case study

Properties to be verified

Operational modes reachability

Fan speed constraint satisfaction

Case study

Properties to be verified

Operational modes reachability

Do these inputs exist?

Fan speed constraint satisfaction

Monotonicity

Do $t_0 < t_1$ exist such that $s_0 > s_1$?

Case study

Properties to be verified

Operational modes reachability

Fan speed constraint satisfaction

Monotonicity

Do $t_0 < t_1$ exist such that $s_0 > s_1$?

Softmax overflow

Case study

Properties to be verified

Operational modes reachability

Do these inputs exist?

Fan speed constraint satisfaction

Monotonicity

Do $t_0 < t_1$ exist such that $s_0 > s_1$?

Softmax overflow

Robustness

Case study

Properties to be verified

Fan speed constraint satisfaction

Monotonicity

Do $t_0 < t_1$ exist such that $s_0 > s_1$?

Softmax overflow

Robustness

Case study

Properties to be verified

Operational modes reachability

Do these inputs exist?

Fan speed constraint satisfaction

Monotonicity

Softmax overflow

Robustness

They help to better understanding the NN

They represent problems

Approaches to verify these properties

Approaches to verify these properties

 Keras

NN design

PLC source code

Executable

Approaches to verify these properties

Different methods were applied and compared:

NN design

PLC source code

Executable

Approaches to verify these properties

Different methods were applied and compared:

1. **nnenum**: an open-source **NN verification** tool for **ReLU** NNs from Stony Brook University
<https://github.com/stanleybak/nnenum>

nnenum

NN design

PLC source code

Executable

Approaches to verify these properties

Different methods were applied and compared:

1. **nnenum**: an open-source **NN verification** tool for **ReLU** NNs from Stony Brook University
<https://github.com/stanleybak/nnenum>
2. **PLCverif**: an open-source formal **verification tool** for **PLC programs** from CERN <https://gitlab.com/plcverif-oss>

nnenum

NN design

PV

PLC source code

Executable

Approaches to verify these properties

Different methods were applied and compared:

1. **nenum**: an open-source **NN verification** tool for **ReLU** NNs from Stony Brook University
<https://github.com/stanleybak/nenum>
2. **PLCverif**: an open-source formal **verification tool** for **PLC programs** from CERN <https://gitlab.com/plcverif-oss>
3. **Z3**: an open-source **theorem prover** from Microsoft Research <https://github.com/Z3Prover/z3>
4. **Testing**: traditional testing techniques

nenum

NN design

PLC source code

Executable

Ignacio D. Lopez-Miguel et al. “*Verification of Neural Networks Meets PLC Code: An LHC Cooling Tower Control System at CERN*”. In *EANN 2023: Engineering Applications of Neural Networks conference*
https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-031-34204-2_35

nenum

nenum

Property encoding (vnnlib)

```
(declare-const X_0 Real)
(declare-const X_1 Real)
(declare-const X_2 Real)
(declare-const Y_0 Real)
(declare-const Y_1 Real)
(declare-const Y_2 Real)
(assert (>= X_0 20.0))
(assert (<= X_0 25.0))
(assert (>= X_1 23))
(assert (<= X_1 27))
(assert (>= X_2 8.0))
(assert (<= X_2 21.0))
(assert (>= Y_0 Y_1))
(assert (>= Y_0 Y_2))
```

nenum

Property encoding (vnnlib)

```
(declare-const X_0 Real)
(declare-const X_1 Real)
(declare-const X_2 Real)
(declare-const Y_0 Real)
(declare-const Y_1 Real)
(declare-const Y_2 Real)
(assert (>= X_0 20.0))
(assert (<= X_0 25.0))
(assert (>= X_1 23))
(assert (<= X_1 27))
(assert (>= X_2 8.0))
(assert (<= X_2 21.0))
(assert (>= Y_0 Y_1))
(assert (>= Y_0 Y_2))
```

} Inputs

nenum

Property encoding (vnnlib)

```
(declare-const X_0 Real)
(declare-const X_1 Real)
(declare-const X_2 Real)
(declare-const Y_0 Real)
(declare-const Y_1 Real)
(declare-const Y_2 Real)
(assert (>= X_0 20.0))
(assert (<= X_0 25.0))
(assert (>= X_1 23))
(assert (<= X_1 27))
(assert (>= X_2 8.0))
(assert (<= X_2 21.0))
(assert (>= Y_0 Y_1))
(assert (>= Y_0 Y_2))
```

Inputs

Outputs

nenum

Property encoding (vnnlib)

```
(declare-const X_0 Real)
(declare-const X_1 Real)
(declare-const X_2 Real)
(declare-const Y_0 Real)
(declare-const Y_1 Real)
(declare-const Y_2 Real)
(assert (>= X_0 20.0))
(assert (<= X_0 25.0))
(assert (>= X_1 23))
(assert (<= X_1 27))
(assert (>= X_2 8.0))
(assert (<= X_2 21.0))
(assert (>= Y_0 Y_1))
(assert (>= Y_0 Y_2))
```

Inputs

Outputs

Range of the inputs:

$$25 \geq x_0 \geq 20$$
$$27 \geq x_1 \geq 23$$
$$21 \geq x_2 \geq 8$$

nenum

Property encoding (vnnlib)

```
(declare-const X_0 Real)
(declare-const X_1 Real)
(declare-const X_2 Real)
(declare-const Y_0 Real)
(declare-const Y_1 Real)
(declare-const Y_2 Real)
(assert (>= X_0 20.0))
(assert (<= X_0 25.0))
(assert (>= X_1 23))
(assert (<= X_1 27))
(assert (>= X_2 8.0))
(assert (<= X_2 21.0))
(assert (>= Y_0 Y_1))
(assert (>= Y_0 Y_2))
```

Inputs

Outputs

Range of the inputs:
 $25 \geq x_0 \geq 20$
 $27 \geq x_1 \geq 23$
 $21 \geq x_2 \geq 8$

Property to verify:
 $y_0 \geq y_1 \wedge y_0 \geq y_2$
*It is possible that the selected mode is **ventilation***

nenum

Property encoding (vnnlib)

```
(declare-const X_0 Real)
(declare-const X_1 Real)
(declare-const X_2 Real)
(declare-const Y_0 Real)
(declare-const Y_1 Real)
(declare-const Y_2 Real)
(assert (>= X_0 20.0))
(assert (<= X_0 25.0))
(assert (>= X_1 23))
(assert (<= X_1 27))
(assert (>= X_2 8.0))
(assert (<= X_2 21.0))
(assert (>= Y_0 Y_1))
(assert (>= Y_0 Y_2))
```

Inputs

Outputs

Range of the inputs:

$$25 \geq x_0 \geq 20$$

$$27 \geq x_1 \geq 23$$

$$21 \geq x_2 \geq 8$$

Property to verify:

$$y_0 \geq y_1 \wedge y_0 \geq y_2$$

*It is possible that the selected mode is **ventilation***

Goal

Find an example that satisfies all conditions, i.e., a set of $\{x_0, x_1, x_2\}$ such that $(y_0 \geq y_1 \wedge y_0 \geq y_2)$

nnenum

Property encoding (vnnlib)

```
(declare-const X_0 Real)
(declare-const X_1 Real)
(declare-const X_2 Real)
(declare-const Y_0 Real)
(declare-const Y_1 Real)
(declare-const Y_2 Real)
(assert (>= X_0 20.0))
(assert (<= X_0 25.0))
(assert (>= X_1 23))
(assert (<= X_1 27))
(assert (>= X_2 8.0))
(assert (<= X_2 21.0))
(assert (>= Y_0 Y_1))
(assert (>= Y_0 Y_2))
```

Inputs

Outputs

Range of the inputs:

$$25 \geq x_0 \geq 20$$

$$27 \geq x_1 \geq 23$$

$$21 \geq x_2 \geq 8$$

Property to verify:

$$y_0 \geq y_1 \wedge y_0 \geq y_2$$

It is possible that the selected mode is ventilation

Goal

Find an example that satisfies all conditions, i.e., a set of $\{x_0, x_1, x_2\}$ such that $(y_0 \geq y_1 \wedge y_0 \geq y_2)$

Execution

```
root@7d4848b3ea5f:/work# python3 -m nnenum.nnenum sharedDocker/final/modes.onnx sharedDocker/final/modesReachability_0.vnnlib
Running in parallel with 16 processes
(0.1 sec) Q: 0, Sets: 0/1 (0.0%) ETA: - (expected 1 stars)

Pre-overapproximation simulation found a confirmed counterexample.

Unsafe Base Branch: (Mode: 0)

Total Stars: 1 (0 exact, 1 approx)
Runtime: 0.1 sec
Completed work frac: 1.0
Num Stars Copied Between Processes: 0
Num Lps During Enumeration: 0
Total Num Lps: 0

Result: network is UNSAFE with confirmed counterexample in result.cinput and result.coutput
Input: [22.5, 25.0, 14.5]
Output: [0.7701750993728638, -0.5644218325614929, -1.8442020416259766]
root@7d4848b3ea5f:/work#
```

nnenum

Property encoding (vnnlib)

```
(declare-const X_0 Real)
(declare-const X_1 Real)
(declare-const X_2 Real)
(declare-const Y_0 Real)
(declare-const Y_1 Real)
(declare-const Y_2 Real)
(assert (>= X_0 20.0))
(assert (<= X_0 25.0))
(assert (>= X_1 23))
(assert (<= X_1 27))
(assert (>= X_2 8.0))
(assert (<= X_2 21.0))
(assert (>= Y_0 Y_1))
(assert (>= Y_0 Y_2))
```

Inputs

Outputs

Range of the inputs:

$25 \geq x_0 \geq 20$

$27 \geq x_1 \geq 23$

$21 \geq x_2 \geq 8$

Property to verify:

$y_0 \geq y_1 \wedge y_0 \geq y_2$

It is possible that the selected mode is ventilation

Goal

Find an example that satisfies all conditions, i.e., a set of $\{x_0, x_1, x_2\}$ such that $(y_0 \geq y_1 \wedge y_0 \geq y_2)$

Execution

```
root@7d4848b3ea5f:/work# python3 -m nnenum.nnenum sharedDocker/final/modes.onnx sharedDocker/final/modesReachability_0.vnnlib
Running in parallel with 16 processes
(0.1 sec) Q: 0, Sets: 0/1 (0.0%) ETA: - (expected 1 stars)

Pre-overapproximation simulation found a confirmed counterexample.

Unsafe Base Branch: (Mode: 0)

Total Stars: 1 (0 exact, 1 approx)
Runtime: 0.1 sec
Completed work frac: 1.0
Num Stars Copied Between Processes: 0
Num Lps During Enumeration: 0
Total Num Lps: 0

Result: network is UNSAFE with confirmed counterexample in result.cinput and result.coutput
Input: [22.5, 25.0, 14.5]
Output: [0.7701750993728638, -0.5644218325614929, -1.8442020416259766]
root@7d4848b3ea5f:/work#
```

Evidence

nnenum

Property encoding (vnnlib)

```
(declare-const X_0 Real)
(declare-const X_1 Real)
(declare-const X_2 Real)
(declare-const Y_0 Real)
(declare-const Y_1 Real)
(declare-const Y_2 Real)
(assert (>= X_0 20.0))
(assert (<= X_0 25.0))
(assert (>= X_1 23))
(assert (<= X_1 27))
(assert (>= X_2 8.0))
(assert (<= X_2 21.0))
(assert (>= Y_0 Y_1))
(assert (>= Y_0 Y_2))
```

Inputs

Outputs

Range of the inputs:

$$25 \geq x_0 \geq 20$$

$$27 \geq x_1 \geq 23$$

$$21 \geq x_2 \geq 8$$

Property to verify:

$$y_0 \geq y_1 \wedge y_0 \geq y_2$$

It is possible that the selected mode is ventilation

Goal

Find an example that satisfies all conditions, i.e., a set of $\{x_0, x_1, x_2\}$ such that $(y_0 \geq y_1 \wedge y_0 \geq y_2)$

Execution

```
root@7d4848b3ea5f:/work# python3 -m nnenum.nnenum sharedDocker/final/modes.onnx sharedDocker/final/modesReachability_0.vnnlib
Running in parallel with 16 processes
(0.1 sec) Q: 0, Sets: 0/1 (0.0%) ETA: - (expected 1 stars)
Pre-overapproximation simulation found a confirmed counterexample.
Unsafe Base Branch: (Mode: 0)
Total Stars: 1 (0 exact, 1 approx)
Runtime: 0.1 sec
Completed work frac: 1.0
Num Stars Copied Between Processes: 0
Num Lps During Enumeration: 0
Total Num Lps: 0
Result: network is UNSAFE with confirmed counterexample in result.cinput and result.coutput
Input: [22.5, 25.0, 14.5]
Output: [0.7701750993728638, -0.5644218325614929, -1.8442020416259766]
root@7d4848b3ea5f:/work#
```

Evidence

Pros:

- Very efficient
- Scalable

Cons:

- Limited to certain architectures
- No loops
- No complex properties

Roadmap

Conclusions (1)

Conclusions (1)

- **Formal verification** (e.g. model checking) can be used **to verify critical software** (critical PLC programs)
- There are not commercial tools (yet) for PLC programs, this is why we developed **PLCverif**
- **PLCverif has been applied to many critical PLC programs** at CERN and outside CERN

Conclusions (1)

- **Formal verification** (e.g. model checking) can be used **to verify critical software** (critical PLC programs)
- There are not commercial tools (yet) for PLC programs, this is why we developed **PLCverif**
- **PLCverif has been applied to many critical PLC programs** at CERN and outside CERN
- Still many **challenges**:
 - **State space explosion** problem (verification performance)
 - Properties **specification**
 - Automatic generation of models
 - **Counterexample analysis** (what do we do when we find a problem?)

Conclusions (2)

Conclusions (2)

1. **Important to verify neural networks** in critical systems to:
 - **guarantee properties** such as robustness, stability, safety, etc.
 - have a **better understanding** of the behavior of the NN

Conclusions (2)

1. **Important to verify neural networks** in critical systems to:
 - **guarantee properties** such as robustness, stability, safety, etc.
 - have a **better understanding** of the behavior of the NN

Simulation.input1	Floating-point nu...	21.3	21.3	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Simulation.input2	Floating-point nu...	23.0	23.0	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Simulation.input3	Floating-point nu...	8.0	8.0	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
NN_Result_DB.fan_speed	Floating-point nu...	0.00262890317651313		<input type="checkbox"/>	
NN_Result_DB.modes[0]	Floating-point nu...	6.01462636744791E-08		<input type="checkbox"/>	
NN_Result_DB.modes[1]	Floating-point nu...	0.00348845387816139		<input type="checkbox"/>	
NN_Result_DB.modes[2]	Floating-point nu...	0.996511485975575		<input type="checkbox"/>	

2. We use **simulators** (e.g. Siemens PLCSIM advanced) **to confirm the property violations** (counterexamples)

Conclusions (2)

1. Important to verify neural networks in critical systems to:
 - **guarantee properties** such as robustness, stability, safety, etc.
 - have a **better understanding** of the behavior of the NN

Simulation.input1	Floating-point nu...	21.3	21.3	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Simulation.input2	Floating-point nu...	23.0	23.0	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Simulation.input3	Floating-point nu...	8.0	8.0	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
NN_Result_DB.fan_speed	Floating-point nu...	0.00262890317651313		<input type="checkbox"/>	
NN_Result_DB.modes[0]	Floating-point nu...	6.01462636744791E-08		<input type="checkbox"/>	
NN_Result_DB.modes[1]	Floating-point nu...	0.00348845387816139		<input type="checkbox"/>	
NN_Result_DB.modes[2]	Floating-point nu...	0.996511485975575		<input type="checkbox"/>	

2. We use **simulators** (e.g. Siemens PLCSIM advanced) **to confirm the property violations** (counterexamples)

3. We analyzed **different verification tools**

	performance	scalability	expressiveness	same types?	plug-and-play?
PLCverif	low	low	high	yes	yes
nnenum	very high	high	low	no	no
Z3	medium	medium	low	no	no
Testing	high	very low	medium	no	no

Conclusions (2)

1. Important to verify neural networks in critical systems to:
 - guarantee properties such as robustness, stability, safety, etc.
 - have a better understanding of the behavior of the NN

Simulation.input1	Floating-point nu...	21.3	21.3	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Simulation.input2	Floating-point nu...	23.0	23.0	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Simulation.input3	Floating-point nu...	8.0	8.0	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
NN_Result_DB.fan_speed	Floating-point nu...	0.00262890317651313		<input type="checkbox"/>	
NN_Result_DB.modes[0]	Floating-point nu...	6.01462636744791E-08		<input type="checkbox"/>	
NN_Result_DB.modes[1]	Floating-point nu...	0.00348845387816139		<input type="checkbox"/>	
NN_Result_DB.modes[2]	Floating-point nu...	0.996511485975575		<input type="checkbox"/>	

2. We use **simulators** (e.g. Siemens PLCSIM advanced) to confirm the property violations (counterexamples)

3. We analyzed **different verification tools**

	performance	scalability	expressiveness	same types?	plug-and-play?
PLCverif	low	low	high	yes	yes
nnenum	very high	high	low	no	no
Z3	medium	medium	low	no	no
Testing	high	very low	medium	no	no

Ignacio D. Lopez-Miguel et al. "Verification of Neural Networks Meets PLC Code: An LHC Cooling Tower Control System at CERN". In EANN 2023: Engineering Applications of Neural Networks conference https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-031-34204-2_35

4. We have applied to a real **case study** for industrial controls at **CERN**

Future work

Future work

“Traditional” PLC-based controllers

NN-based controllers

Towards reliable and safe control software

Future work

“Traditional” PLC-based controllers

Formal specification

Source code

Executable

NN-based controllers

NN design

Source code

Executable

Towards **reliable and safe control software**

Future work

“Traditional” PLC-based controllers

NN-based controllers

Towards **reliable and safe control software**